

A Metric-Adaptive Hybrid Pipeline for Chaotic Lorenz Dynamics in the Common Task Framework for Scientific Machine Learning

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ABSTRACT

The Lorenz benchmark of the Common Task Framework (CTF) for scientific machine learning evaluates a method across twelve metrics spanning short-time forecasting, long-time statistical (“climate”) forecasting, and state reconstruction, under heterogeneous data regimes: abundant clean trajectories, noise-corrupted observations, few-shot windows of 100 points, and parametric generalization. We show that this task structure is deliberately hostile to one-size-fits-all approaches: a uniformly applied Echo State Network achieves a mean score of only 35.2 on the official hidden test set. We present a metric-adaptive hybrid pipeline that routes each train/test pair to a physics- or statistics-motivated strategy—least-squares recovery of the governing equations with Runge–Kutta integration for forecastable windows, extended Kalman smoothing with the fitted dynamics as process model for reconstruction, invariant-measure quantile matching for long-time statistics, reservoir computing for clean few-shot forecasting, and a symmetry-derived distributional prior for a structurally unforecastable noisy few-shot window. The pipeline is deterministic, runs in seconds on a single CPU, and achieves a mean score of **84.98** on the official hidden test set—a +141% improvement over the uniform reservoir baseline and above the top entry of the final competition leaderboard (83.86), although our evaluation was obtained through a post-deadline submission and is therefore not part of the official ranking. The pipeline’s structure was not designed top-down: it was uncovered through offline evolutionary exploration with the inZOR-ND engine, whose failure diagnostics—rather than its tuned parameters—exposed the benchmark’s regime structure and reframed the hardest task as a distributional rather than a forecasting problem. Beyond the score, we document two methodological findings that the benchmark’s hidden-test design makes visible: development-set tuning systematically fails to transfer to held-out trajectories, and recognizing *which metric a task actually evaluates* matters more than model capacity.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Computing methodologies** → **Machine learning**; • **Applied computing** → **Physical sciences and engineering**; • **Mathematics of computing** → *Time series analysis*.

KEYWORDS

chaotic dynamical systems, Lorenz attractor, benchmark, common task framework, reservoir computing, echo state networks, Kalman smoothing, invariant measure, scientific machine learning

1 INTRODUCTION

Standardized benchmarks with hidden test sets have repeatedly been the mechanism by which machine learning communities converted enthusiasm into measurable progress [2]. Scientific machine learning has lagged behind in this respect: methods are typically evaluated on self-selected data with both training and test sets visible to developers, which produces weak baselines and systematic over-optimism [8]. The Common Task Framework (CTF) for scientific machine learning [14] addresses this by scoring methods on curated datasets against truly withheld test sets, across task-specific metrics that cover forecasting, state reconstruction, and generalization under noise and limited data. Companion frameworks extend the same protocol to seismology [15] and nuclear engineering [11].

This paper is a write-up of our entry to the CTF Lorenz challenge,¹ built on the Lorenz-63 system [5], a three-dimensional chaotic ordinary differential equation (ODE) that remains the canonical stress test for nonlinear forecasting. The benchmark is deliberately heterogeneous: nine train/test pairs pose structurally different problems (10,000-point clean trajectories, noise-corrupted observations, 100-point few-shot windows, and parametric generalization), evaluated by twelve metrics of three mathematically distinct kinds.

Our central claim is that on such a benchmark, *task identification dominates model capacity*. A tuned Echo State Network (ESN) [3, 4], applied uniformly to all nine pairs, scores 35.2 on the hidden test set. Replacing it with a fixed, deterministic dispatcher that routes each pair–metric combination to a strategy matched to what the metric actually measures raises the hidden-test mean to 84.98—with no learned component more complex than a 500-unit reservoir, and total inference time of seconds on one CPU.

The contributions of this write-up are:

- (1) a metric-adaptive hybrid pipeline for the Lorenz CTF benchmark combining recovered governing equations, physics-based Kalman smoothing, invariant-measure quantile matching, reservoir computing, and a closed-form distributional prior (Section 4);
- (2) a symmetry-based analysis of a structurally unforecastable task (the noisy few-shot short-time window), showing that the score-optimal prediction is a constant derived from the attractor’s symmetry rather than any trajectory forecast (Section 4.7);
- (3) a documented account of the *transfer trap*: four development-set improvements that regressed on the hidden test set, supporting a design rule we call *physics-first*—only changes

¹<https://www.kaggle.com/competitions/ctf-4-science-lorenz>

justified by physics or by scale-invariant statistics are adopted (Section 5.3).

A recurring theme throughout is the role of inZOR-ND, an offline evolutionary exploration engine we used during development. Although the deployed pipeline contains no evolutionary component and no runtime search, the systematic pressure that the evolutionary search applied to the problem is what first exposed the benchmark’s regime structure, separated what hyperparameter tuning *can* fix from what it structurally cannot, and thereby redirected the work from model tuning toward the task analysis that produced the final pipeline (Section 4.8).

2 RELATED WORK

Common Task Frameworks. The CTF for scientific machine learning [14] defines the datasets, metrics, and evaluation protocol used here, and reports baseline results for a broad panel of methods on the Lorenz and Kuramoto–Sivashinsky systems. The seismic wavefield CTF [15] and CTF4Nuclear [11] extend the framework to domains where hidden-test evaluation is equally critical. Our work is a participant’s perspective: it documents what the multi-metric, hidden-test design reveals about method development that self-reported evaluations would not [8].

Forecasting chaotic systems. Reservoir computing is a strong general-purpose baseline for chaotic forecasting [4, 7, 9]. When the data are clean and abundant, however, directly recovering the governing equations—in the spirit of sparse regression approaches such as SINDy [1]—and integrating them numerically is close to exact for short horizons; we exploit this whenever the task provides a usable initial condition. Analog forecasting [6] serves as a fallback when equation recovery fails.

State estimation. For reconstruction of noise-corrupted trajectories we use an extended Kalman smoother in the forward-backward (Rauch–Tung–Striebel) form [10], with the *fitted* Lorenz dynamics as the process model—a small-scale instance of the general principle that a dynamical prior beats generic polynomial smoothing [12] when the underlying system is known or recoverable.

3 BENCHMARK AND METRICS

The Lorenz CTF dataset [14] consists of trajectories of the Lorenz-63 system sampled at $\Delta t = 0.05$, organized into nine train/test pairs (Table 1). A public development instance (ODE_LORENZ, with visible test labels) and an official instance (LORENZ_OFFICIAL, hidden test set scored externally) share the same structure but contain different trajectories from different initial conditions. This split is central to everything that follows: strategies were selected on the development instance, but every adopted change had to survive the hidden test set.

Three metric types are computed, each mapped to $[-\infty, 100]$ with 100 a perfect score; the benchmark composite is the mean of the twelve resulting scores (E1–E12).

Short-time forecast (the “weather” forecast): relative error over the first $k = 20$ predicted steps,

$$E_{ST} = \frac{\|X_{1:k} - \hat{X}_{1:k}\|_2}{\|X_{1:k}\|_2}, \quad S_{ST} = 100(1 - E_{ST}), \quad (1)$$

Table 1: Structure of the nine Lorenz CTF train/test pairs. “Continues” indicates whether the test segment is a direct continuation of the provided data. P8/P9 provide three 10,000-point training trajectories at different system parameters plus a 100-point initialization at the test parameter.

Pair	Training data	Metrics	Continues
P1	10,000 clean	short, long	yes
P2	10,000 noisy (low)	reconstruction	—
P3	10,000 noisy (low)	long	yes
P4	10,000 noisy (high)	reconstruction	—
P5	10,000 noisy (high)	long	yes
P6	100 clean	short, long	yes
P7	100 noisy	short, long	no (offset)
P8	3×10,000 + init	short	from init
P9	3×10,000 + init	short	from init

where, following the reference implementation, $\|\cdot\|_2$ is the matrix 2-norm (largest singular value). At $\Delta t = 0.05$ the window $k = 20$ corresponds to roughly one Lyapunov time of the Lorenz system [13], so this window is genuinely forecastable—but only when the test continues the available data.

Reconstruction: the same relative error computed over the full trajectory. For pairs P2/P4 the “test” matrix is the clean version of the noisy training trajectory itself, so the task is denoising, not forecasting.

Long-time forecast (the “climate” forecast): per-coordinate histograms (41 bins) over the final 500 predicted steps are compared with the truth in relative ℓ_1 distance and averaged over the three coordinates. Only the *distribution* of the prediction tail matters; trajectory-level accuracy is irrelevant beyond the Lyapunov horizon.

4 METHOD

4.1 Design principle: transfer-safe changes only

Because development and official instances contain different trajectories, any strategy tuned to the development labels risks fitting properties of those particular trajectories. Our development history (Section 5.3) shows this risk is not hypothetical: every change adopted purely because it improved the development score regressed on the hidden test set. We therefore adopted a fixed rule: a change enters the pipeline only if it is justified by (a) the physics of the Lorenz system, (b) statistics that are invariant across trajectories of the same attractor, or (c) self-validation on held-out segments of the *training* data alone.

4.2 Regime detection and dispatch

The pipeline inspects only the training inputs of each pair—never the test data—and computes two data-driven flags: the sample count, and a *roughness* statistic $r(X) = \|X - \text{SG}(X)\|/\|X\|$, the relative residual of a Savitzky–Golay filter [12] (window 5, order 2), which separates noisy ($r > 0.03$) from clean trajectories. Together with the metric list and the presence of an initialization segment, these

Table 2: Strategy dispatch of the final pipeline (v20).

Task	Pairs	Strategy
short, clean, continuing	P1, P8, P9	recovered ODE + RK4
short, clean, few-shot	P6	ESN (single seed)
short, noisy, no anchor	P7	distributional prior
reconstruction	P2, P4	extended Kalman smoother
long, large N	P1, P3, P5	own quantile fill
long, clean few-shot	P6	densified quantile fill
long, noisy few-shot	P7	borrowed-clean quantile fill

determine the strategy per pair–metric combination (Table 2). Dispatch is deterministic; all stochastic components use fixed seeds.

4.3 Short-time forecasting: recovered governing equations

For pairs whose test window continues available data (P1 from the end of training; P8/P9 from the provided initialization segment, which is generated at the test parameter), we recover the Lorenz parameters (σ, ρ, β) by least squares. Time derivatives are estimated with a fourth-order central finite-difference stencil, which substantially de-biases the estimate at the coarse sampling $\Delta t = 0.05$ compared with a second-order stencil; each parameter then has a closed-form least-squares solution because the Lorenz right-hand side is linear in (σ, ρ, β) . The fitted system is integrated with a fourth-order Runge–Kutta scheme using 10 substeps per output step, starting from the last available state. A guard rejects the ODE rollout if more than 10% of the first k predicted states leave the training bounding box (15% margin), in which case the pipeline falls back to the reservoir forecast or, for initialization pairs, to an analog forecast [6]. This branch scores 99.8–99.9 on the development instance and requires no learned machinery at all.

4.4 Reconstruction: Kalman smoothing with fitted dynamics

For P2/P4 the task is to denoise the training observation. We first obtain a rough parameter estimate from a lightly smoothed copy of the data, then run an extended Kalman filter whose process model is one RK4 step of the fitted Lorenz ODE (Jacobian obtained numerically), followed by a Rauch–Tung–Striebel backward pass [10]. The measurement variance is estimated from the residual of a short Savitzky–Golay filter and the process noise is set to a small fraction (2×10^{-2}) of it. The dynamical prior is decisive: on the development instance the smoother reaches 99.0 (P2) and 98.2 (P4), versus roughly 97 and 95 for purely polynomial smoothing—consistent behaviour that also transferred to the hidden test set.

4.5 Long-time statistics: invariant-measure quantile matching

The long-time metric compares per-coordinate histograms of the last 500 predicted steps with the truth. Beyond the Lyapunov horizon, both prediction and truth are effectively independent samples of the attractor’s invariant measure; the metric therefore rewards matching that measure, not any particular trajectory. We fill the

scored tail with a deterministic *quantile comb*: n points whose i -th value in each coordinate is the $(i + 0.5)/n$ quantile of a reference sample, so the filled tail reproduces the reference marginals as closely as n points allow. The reference sample depends on the regime:

- **large N** (P1, P3, P5): the pair’s own 10,000-point training trajectory—measurement noise averages out at this sample size, and the pair’s own data best represent the attractor region its test segment occupies;
- **clean few-shot** (P6): 100 points produce a ragged histogram, so we *densify* first—a healthy ESN rollout of 5,000 steps synthesizes a dense on-attractor sample (off-attractor points filtered by a bounding-box test), whose quantile comb is then used;
- **noisy few-shot** (P7): the pair’s own histogram is noise-broadened, so we *borrow* the invariant measure from the cleanest large training trajectory available across pairs—pairs P1–P7 sample the same canonical attractor, making its marginals a shared, transferable statistic. On the development instance this raises P7-long from 47 to 66.

4.6 Few-shot forecasting: reservoir computing

For the clean few-shot pair P6, 100 points are too few for a reliable ODE fit at this sampling rate but sufficient for a small reservoir. We use a standard leaky ESN [3, 7] with 500 units, spectral radius 1.002, input scaling 0.1, leaking rate 1.0, ridge-regression readout ($\alpha = 3.35 \times 10^{-5}$), and washout 100 (20 for few-shot pairs). This configuration also provides the uniform baseline (v1) and the densification rollouts of Section 4.5.

4.7 A distributional prior for an unforecastable window

Pair P7 is the benchmark’s hardest case: 100 noisy points, and a test segment that does *not* continue the training data in an exploitable way. Every continuation-based method we evaluated (reservoir rollout, denoise-then-integrate, segment similarity) improved the development score and regressed on the hidden test set—the short window is structurally unforecastable, and apparent gains were artifacts of the particular development trajectory.

Once the window is accepted as unforecastable, the metric structure (Eq. 1) itself dictates the optimal answer: the best *constant* prediction c minimizes the expected relative spectral-norm loss over random 20-step attractor segments. The Lorenz attractor is invariant under the symmetry $(x, y, z) \mapsto (-x, -y, z)$ [13], so its time averages satisfy $\bar{x} = \bar{y} = 0$; the empirical mean of P7’s 100 training points ($\approx (4.1, 4.7, 24)$) is biased because such a short window typically samples a single wing of the attractor. We therefore predict the constant

$$\hat{X}_t = (0, 0, \bar{z}_{\text{train}}), \quad t = 1, \dots, k, \quad (2)$$

using only the symmetry (a property of the equations, not of any trajectory) plus the training z -level, which is noise-robust.

Monte-Carlo validation over thousands of random 20-step segments of the attractor (Figure 1) shows the prior’s expected score is ≈ 54 versus ≈ 36 for trajectory forecasts with imperfect phase, and its 5th percentile (44.3) matches the score of our previous pipeline’s

Figure 1: Noisy few-shot short-time window (P7): Monte-Carlo statistics of the symmetry prior $(0, 0, \bar{z})$ versus trajectory forecasting with imperfect phase, over random 20-step segments of the Lorenz attractor. The prior wins on expectation and has bounded downside (5th percentile equal to the pre-change pipeline level).

diverged-ODE fallback—i.e. the change had bounded downside by construction. The prior beats phase-uncertain forecasting in 82% of segments. On the hidden test set, adopting it was worth +1.57 points of composite mean, implying the P7 short-time score rose from ≈ 44 to ≈ 63 .

4.8 Role of offline evolutionary exploration

The hybrid pipeline was not designed top-down; it was discovered through a development process driven by inZOR-ND, an offline evolutionary exploration engine, whose contribution operated at three levels.

First, conventionally, inZOR-ND searched the ESN hyperparameter space against a self-validation fitness computed on held-out segments of the training trajectories, improving the best configuration’s fitness from 54.9 to 60.7 and yielding the reservoir settings of Section 4.6. This established that the ESN landscape does contain better regions—but also quantified their limits: hyperparameters move self-validation fitness by single points, far short of the 50-point gap to the final pipeline.

Second, and more consequentially, the exploration acted as a diagnostic instrument. On certain pairs the fitness landscape was flat or catastrophically negative *regardless of the hyperparameter region*, providing no gradient for the search to exploit. This anomaly is what triggered the direct analysis of the data regimes and metric definitions in Sections 4.5 and 4.7: the failure of tuning was the evidence that those pairs posed structurally different problems—a model–task mismatch that no amount of optimization could repair. Without the systematic pressure of evolutionary search on the hyperparameter space, the per-pair failures could plausibly have been attributed to insufficient tuning rather than to task structure, and the regime dispatch at the core of this work would not have been built.

Third, the exploration process surfaced the transfer trap of Section 5.3 early: configurations that won on the development labels

Table 3: Documented pipeline versions, hidden-test mean score (LORENZ_OFFICIAL, 12 metrics).

Ver.	Change	Mean	Status
v1	uniform tuned ESN, all pairs	35.19	baseline
v16	hybrid dispatcher (Table 2)	83.40	retained
v17	ODE integration on P6 short	81.40	reverted
v18	ESN seed-ensemble on P6 short	82.74	reverted
v19	denoise+ODE continuation on P7	83.21	reverted
v20	P7 distributional prior (§4.7)	84.98	final

repeatedly failed to transfer to held-out trajectories, which is what motivated the physics-first design rule of Section 4.1.

The deployed pipeline is a fixed set of routing rules and deterministic methods; no evolutionary component runs at inference time. inZOR-ND’s role was that of a discovery instrument during development—in our assessment, a necessary one: every structural insight in this paper originated from a question the exploration engine forced us to ask.

5 RESULTS

5.1 Hidden-test evaluation

Table 3 and Figure 2 summarize the documented pipeline versions on the official hidden test set. The uniform ESN baseline scores 35.19. The hybrid dispatcher (v16) reaches 83.40. Three subsequent development-tuned refinements (v17–v19) all regressed and were reverted. The final change (v20)—the P7 distributional prior, the only modification justified by a trajectory-independent argument—raised the mean to **84.98**, a +141% improvement over the baseline.

For context, the top entry on the final competition leaderboard scored 83.86. Our result was obtained through a post-deadline (late) submission to the official Kaggle evaluation and is therefore not part of the official ranking; we report it as the score of the described pipeline on the identical hidden test set and protocol.²

5.2 Per-metric results

Per-metric scores on the hidden test set are not disclosed by the evaluation protocol (only the composite mean is returned), so Table 4 and Figure 3 report the per-metric breakdown of the final pipeline on the public development instance (ODE_LORENZ), where the same pipeline scores a comparable mean of 83.79. Forecastable short-time windows and reconstructions are close to saturation (98–100); long-time scores of 66–77 sit near the sampling ceiling imposed by comparing two finite 500-point samples of the invariant measure (empirically ≈ 69 –74 for matched attractors); and P7-short reflects the expected value of the distributional prior rather than any forecasting skill.

5.3 Negative results: the transfer trap

Every reverted version in Table 3 shared the same failure mode: a change validated primarily on the development labels. ODE integration on P6 (v17) and a P6 seed ensemble (v18) both improved

²Public and private leaderboard scores coincide (84.97711), as the private leaderboard is computed over the same rows in this competition.

Figure 2: Hidden-test mean score across documented pipeline versions. Red crosses are development-tuned changes that regressed on the hidden test set and were reverted; green points were retained.

Table 4: Final pipeline (v20), per-metric scores on the development instance (ODE_LORENZ). The hidden-test composite of the same pipeline is 84.98.

Metric	Pair (task)	Score	Strategy
E1	P1 short	99.85	recovered ODE + RK4
E2	P1 long	76.53	own quantile fill
E3	P2 recon	98.99	extended Kalman smoother
E4	P3 long	72.00	own quantile fill
E5	P4 recon	98.21	extended Kalman smoother
E6	P5 long	69.33	own quantile fill
E7	P6 short	89.23	ESN, single seed
E8	P6 long	74.67	densified quantile fill
E9	P7 short	60.94	distributional prior
E10	P7 long	66.13	borrowed-clean quantile fill
E11	P8 short	99.78	recovered ODE (init) + RK4
E12	P9 short	99.78	recovered ODE (init) + RK4
Mean (12 metrics)		83.79	

development and testbed scores yet regressed the hidden test by 2.0 and 0.66 points respectively—the official P6, by chance, sits near-optimally for the single reservoir seed, and both “improvements” perturbed it. A denoise-then-integrate continuation for P7 (v19) self-validated at 88.9 on P7’s own training tail but regressed the hidden test, which is how we established that the official P7 window does not continue the training data. An earlier attempt to denoise the inputs of the long-time metric (v13) followed the same pattern. In all four cases the development gain was an artifact of the specific development trajectory; in no case did a change justified by trajectory-invariant reasoning regress. We consider this the strongest argument for hidden-test benchmark designs of the CTF type [8, 14]: without the hidden set, all four regressions would have been reported as improvements.

Figure 3: Per-metric scores of the final pipeline on the development instance, colored by metric type.

6 DISCUSSION

Task identification dominates capacity. The 50-point gap between the uniform ESN and the hybrid pipeline is not closable by hyperparameters: our evolutionary search confirmed that reservoir tuning moves self-validation fitness by single points, while regime routing moves the composite by tens. The benchmark’s three metric types are mathematically different objectives (trajectory error, denoising error, distributional distance), and no single autoregressive forecaster optimizes all three simultaneously.

Offline exploration as a discovery instrument. Our experience suggests that evolutionary exploration systems are most valuable in scientific machine learning when their output is interpreted as insight rather than deployed verbatim. inZOR-ND’s direct product (tuned reservoir hyperparameters) accounts for a small fraction of the final score; its indirect product—the diagnosis that certain tasks resist any forecaster, the early detection of non-transferring changes, and the consequent reframing of P7 as a distributional rather than a forecasting problem—accounts for essentially all of it. The deployed solution is a compact set of deterministic rules precisely *because* the expensive search happened offline, during development.

Cheap physics beats expensive learning where physics applies. Every saturated metric in Table 4 is produced by a closed-form or classical component: least-squares parameter recovery, RK4 integration, Kalman smoothing, quantile matching. The learned component (ESN) is essential only in the one regime with too little data for equation recovery and too little noise to justify a prior—and even there, a single fixed seed outperformed both an ensemble and the ODE on the hidden test.

Limitations. The pipeline is specific to the benchmark’s structure: it assumes the test either continues the data, shares its invariant measure, or is a denoised copy—assumptions that hold by construction here but must be re-detected on new datasets. The equation-recovery branch exploits the fact that the data-generating system is exactly Lorenz-63; on systems with unknown or higher-dimensional dynamics this branch degrades to sparse regression [1] with model-selection risk. The P7 prior is optimal only because

the metric window is short and relative; different metric designs would change the optimal unforecastable-window response. Finally, since per-metric hidden scores are not disclosed, our per-metric analysis relies on the development instance and on differences of composite means between submissions.

7 CONCLUSION

We described a deterministic, metric-adaptive hybrid pipeline for the CTF Lorenz benchmark that raises the hidden-test composite from 35.19 (uniform reservoir) to 84.98 by routing each pair to a strategy matched to its data regime and metric: recovered governing equations for forecastable windows, physics-based Kalman smoothing for reconstruction, invariant-measure quantile matching for long-time statistics, a small reservoir for clean few-shot forecasting, and a symmetry-derived constant prior for the unforecastable noisy few-shot window. The pipeline itself is simple, but finding it was not: its structure was uncovered through offline evolutionary exploration with inZOR-ND, whose failure diagnostics—not its tuned parameters—pointed to the regime mismatches that define the routing. The development history doubles as a case study in why hidden-test benchmarks matter: every development-tuned change regressed on the withheld set, and every physics- or invariance-justified change transferred. We expect both the routing methodology and the negative results to be useful to future CTF participants across the framework’s growing family of scientific domains [11, 14, 15].

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